

Flat straplike leaves

Thalassia hemprichii

Oceana serrulata

Halodule uninervis

Gomon Zerb Torti

Very Long leaves (min. 30 cm)

Enhalus acoroides

Gomon zerb gran fey

Spaghetti-like leaves

Syringodium isoetifolium

Gomon zerb spageti

Leaves in fanlike clusters

Thalassodendron ciliatum

Gomon zerb levantay

Oval leaves in pairs

Halophila decipiens

Gomon zerb zorey lapen